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● Preliminary checklist of the subfamily Cassidinae (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) in Southwest Karst National Park (under establishment), Guangxi, China

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Abstract: In this text, thirteen species belonging to seven genera of the subfamily Cassidinae (tribes Aspidomorphini, Basiprionotini, Cassidini, and Hispini) are reported from the Southwest Karst National Park (under establishment), Guangxi Zhuang Autonomous Region, China. Among them, *Platypria aliena* Chen & Sun, 1962, is newly recorded for Guangxi, China.

Keywords: Leaf beetles, new records, taxonomy, tortoise beetles

● 西南岩溶国家公园广西创建评估区龟甲亚科（鞘翅目：叶甲科）种类名录初报

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摘要: 本文记述了采自西南岩溶国家公园广西创建评估区的龟甲亚科 7 属 13 种, 分别隶属于梳龟甲族、锯龟甲族、龟甲族和铁甲族。其中, 并蒂掌铁甲 *Platypria aliena* Chen & Sun, 1962 为广西新记录种。

关键词: 叶甲, 新记录, 分类学, 龟甲

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● Introduction

The subfamily Cassidinae *sensu lato*, comprising over 6,400 species, is the second most diverse subfamily within the Chrysomelidae (Staines 2015; Calcetas *et al.* 2020; Sekerka 2023; Borowiec & Świętojańska 2024). Approximately 500 species are known from China (Chen *et al.* 1986; Staines 2015; Liu *et al.* 2019; Yang *et al.* 2023; Borowiec & Świętojańska 2024). Members of the Cassidinae are phytophagous and include both established and potential agricultural pests. They are also considered reliable indicators of floral diversity.

The Southwest Karst National Park (under establishment) is situated in the Guizhou-Guangxi Karst Evergreen Broad-Leaved Forest region in southwestern China, and is one of the 52 candidate areas for China's national park system.

In 2024, the authors conducted a baseline insect survey in the Guangxi section of Southwest National Park. We collected 13 species from seven genera in the subfamily Cassidinae (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae), including one new provincial species for Guangxi Zhuang Autonomous Region, China.

● Material and methods

The leaf beetles (Cassidinae) were collected in 2024. All adult specimens were preserved in 70% ethanol and determined by Dr. Chao-Kun Yang (Yangtze University, Jingzhou, China). Voucher specimens are deposited in the Insect Collection, College of Agriculture, Yangtze University, Jingzhou, Hubei, China (YZU).

Photographs were taken using a Canon 5D Mark II digital camera equipped with a Canon EF 100 mm f/2.8L IS USM lens. Multiple images were taken at different focal planes with the lowest aperture, and the images were subsequently stacked and composed using Helicon Focus software. All images were subsequently modified and arranged into plates using Adobe Photoshop CC 2019.

● Taxonomy

Tribe Aspidomorhini Chapuis, 1875 梳龟甲族

Genus *Aspidomorpha* Hope, 1840 梳龟甲属

1) *Aspidomorpha* (*s. str.*) *furcata* (Thunberg, 1789) 甘薯梳龟甲

Fig. 1

Cassida furcata Thunberg, 1789: 87. **Type locality:** India.

Cassida dorsata Olivier, 1790: 386.

Cassida micans Fabricius, 1801: 398. **Type locality:** Sumatra, Indonesia.

Aspidomorpha micans: Boheman 1854: 313.

Aspidomorpha [*sic*] *micans*: Morsbach 1865: 114.

Aspidomorpha furcata: Weise 1897: 104.

Aspidomorpha [*sic*] *furcata*: Borowiec 1996: 8.

Aspidomorpha (*Aspidomorpha*) [*sic*] *furcata*: Borowiec 1999: 186.

Material examined. Guangxi, Hechi City, Huanjiang County, Shuiyuan Town, Yuhuan Village (环江县水源镇玉环村), 30.VII.2024, 1♂2♀♀, leg. Guang-Lin Xie; Guangxi, Baise City, Leye City, Xinhua Town, Baini Village (乐业县新化镇百坭村), 12.VIII.2024, 2♀♀, leg. Guang-Lin Xie.

Diagnosis. Body almost circular, narrower than 7 mm. Pronotum and scutellum yellow. Elytral pattern and areolae surrounding elytral punctures yellow, yellow-brown to brown. Explanate margin of elytra with yellowish-brown to dark-brown humeral spots. Ventral surface and legs yellow. Antennae yellow, last segment infuscate to completely black.

Distribution: China: Fujian, Guangdong, Guangxi, Guizhou, Hainan, Hunan, Jiangsu, Jiangxi, Macao, Shanghai, Sichuan, Taiwan, Yunnan, Zhejiang; Bhutan; Cambodia; India; Indonesia; Japan; Laos; Malaysia; Myanmar; Nepal; Sri Lanka; Thailand; Vietnam.

2) *Aspidomorpha* (*s. str.*) *sanctaerucis* (Fabricius, 1792) 金梳龟甲

Fig. 2

Cassida jamaicensis: Olivier, 1790: 386. [preoccupied].

Cassida St. Crucis [*sic*] Fabricius, 1792: 450. **Type locality:** “America insularis” [Saint Croix Island, U.S. Virgin Islands].

Aspidomorpha St. Crucis: Boheman 1854: 287.

Aspidomorpha bajula Boheman, 1854: 288.

Aspidomorpha fraternal Baly, 1863: 11. **Type locality:** Cambodia.

Aspidomorpha Santae-Crucis [*sic*]: Duvivier 1891: 50.

Aspidomorpha sanctae-crucis fraterna: Gressitt 1939: 140.

Aspidomorpha [*sic*] *sanctaerucis*: Borowiec 1996: 12.

Aspidomorpha (*Aspidomorpha*) [*sic*] *sanctaerucis*: Borowiec 1999: 198.

Material examined. Guangxi, Hechi City, Huanjiang County, Shuiyuan Town, Yuhuan Village (环江县水源镇玉环村), 30.VII.2024, 1♀, leg. Guang-Lin Xie; Guangxi, Baise City, Leye City, Xinhua Town, Baini Village (乐业县新化镇百坭村), 12.VIII.2024, 1♂1♀, leg. Guang-Lin Xie; Guangxi, Baise City, Leye County, Yachang Township (乐业县雅长乡), 8.VIII.2024, 1♂2♀, leg. Guang-Lin Xie.

Diagnosis. Body circular. Pronotum and scutellum yellow to yellowish-brown, rarely reddish-brown. Elytral disc monochromatic yellow, yellowish-red to yellowish-brown. Explanate margin of elytra with reddish-brown humeral and posterolateral spots; humeral spots usually hammer-shaped, often with small yellow window close to humeral angle. Ventral surface yellow to yellowish-brown. Legs yellow. Antennae yellow, last two segments black.

Distribution: China: Fujian, Guangdong, Guangxi, Hainan, Hunan, Sichuan, Yunnan; America?; Bangladesh; Bhutan; Cambodia; India; Indonesia; Laos; Malaysia; Myanmar; Nepal; Philippines; Pakistan; Sri Lanka; Thailand; Vietnam.

Genus *Laccoptera* Boheman, 1855 腊龟甲属

3) *Laccoptera* (*Sindiola*) *hospita* Boheman, 1855 淡腹双梳龟甲

Fig. 3

Laccoptera hospita Boheman, 1855: 68. **Type locality:** China.

Laccoptera (*Laccoptera*) *hospita*: Spaeth 1914b: 82.

Laccoptera vigintisex-notata var. *hospita*: Maulik 1918: 318.

Sindiola hospita: Spaeth 1932: 228.

Laccoptera vigintisexnotata ssp. *puncticolle* Gressitt, 1938: 189. **Type locality:** Hainan, China.

Laccoptera vigintisexnotata puncticollis [*sic*]: Gressitt 1939: 141.

Sandiolavigintisexnotata hospita [*sic*]: Hua 1989: 87.

Laccoptera (*Sindiola*) *hospita*: Borowiec 1999: 225.

Material examined. Guangxi, Hechi City, Jinchengjiang District, Bagong Town, Jiugong (河池市金城江区拔贡镇久贡), 26.VII.2024, 1♀, leg. Guang-Lin Xie.

Diagnosis. Body triangular. Pronotum yellow or yellowish-brown with six spots. Elytral disc yellow or yellowish-brown with a fairly constant pattern composed of a spot, sometimes divided into four smaller spots. A spot between intervals 1 and 4 on the slope, a spot, sometimes connected with elongate posthumeral spots, on intervals 5-7 at half length of disc, a spot on the humeral callus, and an elongate, oblique spot in the posthumeral part of disc, extending from the base of humeral callus to half length of disc. An additional small spot may be present

FIGURES 1–8. 1 *Aspidomorpha* (*s. str.*) *furcata* (Thunberg, 1789) 2 *A.* (*s. str.*) *sanctaecrucis* (Fabricius, 1792) 3 *Laccoptera* (*Sindiola*) *hospita* Boheman, 1855 4 *L.* (*Laccopteroidea*) *nepalensis* Boheman, 1855 5 *Basiprionota chinensis* (Fabricius, 1798) 6 *B. pudica* (Spaeth, 1925) 7 *Cassida circumdata* Herbst, 1799 8 *C. obtusata* Boheman, 1854.

between intervals 1 and 2 in the posterior part of the disc and 3-5 small spots in the anterior part of the disc. Explanate margin with posterolateral spots and without humeral and sutural spots. Ventral surface and legs uniformly yellow. Antennae yellow, four last segments black.

Distribution: China: Guangdong, Guangxi, Guizhou, Hainan, Sichuan, Yunnan; Cambodia; Laos; Thailand; Vietnam.

4) *Lacoptera (Lacopteroidea) nepalensis* Boheman, 1855 甘薯腊龟甲

Fig. 4

Cassida quadrimaculata Thunberg, 1789: 86. **Type locality:** China.

Lacoptera chinensis Fabricius, 1798: 84. **Type locality:** China.

Lacoptera nepalensis Boheman, 1855: 76. **Type locality:** Nepal.

Lacoptera quadrimaculata: Boheman 1856: 156.

Lacoptera Thunbergi Spaeth, 1914a: 15.

Lacoptera (Lacoptera) nepalensis: Spaeth 1914b: 82.

Lacoptera (Lacoptera) quadrimaculata: Spaeth 1914b: 82.

Lacoptera 4-maculata: Medvedev & Dan 1982: 96.

Lacoptera quadrimaculata nepalensis: Zia & Wu 1981: 521.

Lacoptera quadrimaculata quadrimaculata: Chen *et al.* 1986: 576, 635.

Lacoptera quatuordecimmaculata [sic]: Medvedev 2002: 36.

Material examined. Guangxi, Hechi City, Fengshan County, Sanmenhai Town, Liangli Village (凤山县凤城镇良利村), 25.IV.2024, 1♀, leg. Guang-Lin Xie; Guangxi, Baise City, Xinhua Town, Dianping Village (乐业县新化镇店坪村), 7.VIII.2024, 1♂1♀, leg. Guang-Lin Xie; Guangxi, Baise City, Leye County, Xinhua Town, Baini Village (乐业县新化镇百坭村), 12.VIII.2024, 1♂3♀♀, leg. Guang-Lin Xie.

Diagnosis. Body almost triangular. Pronotum yellowish-brown or brown, usually with two small black spots. Scutellum yellowish-brown or brown. Ground colour of elytral disc yellowish-brown or brown. disc with a spot in the postscutellar area, a spot at 4/5 length of interval 3, a spot on humeral callus, a spot at half length between interval 5 and 6, and two spots along the margin of disc, first slightly below the humeral spots of marginalia, second close to the posterolateral spots of marginalia. Explanate margin with brown humeral, posterolateral, and always with sutural spots. Ventral surface mostly yellow, usually with black metathorax and brown basal margins of abdominal sternites. Legs yellow. Antennae yellow, usually three or four last segments infuscate or black.

Distribution: China: Fujian, Guangdong, Guangxi, Guizhou, Hainan, Hubei, Hunan, Jiangsu, Jiangxi, Liaoning, Sichuan, Taiwan, Yunnan, Zhejiang; India; Indonesia; Japan; Laos; Malaysia; Myanmar; Nepal; Pakistan; Singapore; Thailand; Vietnam.

Tribe Basiprionotini 锯龟甲族

Genus *Basiprionota* Chevrolat, 1836 锯龟甲属

5) *Basiprionota chinensis* (Fabricius, 1798) 大锯龟甲

Fig. 5

Cassida chinensis Fabricius, 1798: 84. **Type locality:** China.

Prioptera satrapa Boheman, 1862: 17. **Type locality:** Shanghai, China.

Prioptera chinensis: Weise 1910: 42.

Prioptera bimaculata Gressitt, 1938: 575.

Basiprionota chinensis: Gressitt 1952: 457.

Basiprionota (s. str.) chinensis: Gressitt & Kimoto 1963: 947.

Material examined. Guangxi, Baise City, Leye County, Yachang Township (乐业县雅长乡), 17.IV.2024, 1♀, leg.

Guang-Lin Xie.

Diagnosis. Body oval. Pronotum with paired dark brown maculae on disc. Elytra adorned with narrow black basal margin, a large midposterior lateral black spot per side, and two longitudinal elevated carinae forming a tumid dorsal profile; humeral tubercle prominent; basal depression shallow, median and lateral depressions distinct; punctures coarse, dense, irregularly distributed. Metaventricle with three posterior black spots. Abdominal ventrites III–V bearing lateral and posterior margin black spots. Femora with a large ventromedial black spot; tibial apices and tarsi darkened. Antennae slender, segments 1–9 pale brownish-yellow, 10 and 11 black.

Distribution: China: Fujian, Guangdong, Guangxi, Guizhou, Hainan, Hong Kong, Hubei, Hunan, Jiangsu, Jiangxi, Shaanxi, Shanghai, Sichuan, Zhejiang; Philippines; Vietnam.

6) *Basiprionota pudica* (Spaeth, 1925) 西南锯龟甲

Fig. 6

Prioptera pudica Spaeth, 1925: 403.

Basiprionota (s. str.) *pudica*: Chen *et al.* 1986: 447.

Basiprionota pudica: Peng & Liu 1992: 612.

Material examined. Guangxi, Baise City, Leye County, Gantian Town, Sihe Village (乐业县甘田镇四合村), 22. I V.2024, 1♀, leg. Guang-Lin Xie; Guangxi, Hechi City, Fengshan County, Fengcheng Town, Xinglong Village (凤山县凤城镇兴隆村), 25.IV.2024, 1♀, leg. Guang-Lin Xie; Guangxi, Hechi City, Dahua County, Yalong Township, Pantu Village (大化县雅龙乡盘兔村), 20.VII.2024, 1♀, leg. Guanglin Xie; Guangxi, Baise City, Leye county, Yachang Township (乐业县雅长乡), 8.VIII.2024, 1♂2♀♀, leg. Guang-Lin Xie.

Diagnosis. Body elliptical. Pronotum disc dark brown, finely and sparsely punctured; basal margin deeply emarginate. Scutellum triangular, slightly convex medially. Elytra basal margin black, serrated to the humeral angle; disc weakly tumid but not tuberculate; deep base, median, and lateral depressions filled with coarse punctures; discal punctures moderately coarse, finer on slopes. Explanate margin of elytra with a large, rectangular, black spot in the mid-posterior region. Ventral surface pale brownish-yellow, metaventricle and mid-ventral abdominal region dark brown to black. Antennae yellow, last two segments black.

Distribution. China: Guangxi, Guizhou, Hubei, Hunan, Sichuan, Yunnan; India.

Tribe Cassidini Gyllenhal, 1813 龟甲族

Genus *Cassida* Linnaeus, 1758 龟甲属

7) *Cassida circumdata* Herbst, 1799 甘薯台龟甲

Fig. 7

Cassida circumdata Herbst, 1799: 268. **Type locality:** India.

Cassida trivittata Fabricius, 1801: 397.

Cassida U-fuscum [sic] Wiedemann, 1823: 74. **Type locality:** Bengal, India.

Aspidomorpha effusa Boheman, 1854: 320. **Type locality:** Java, Indonesia.

Coptocyclus circumdata: Boheman 1855: 279.

Coptocyclus effusa: Boheman 1856: 181.

Coptocyclus luzonica Eschscholtz: Gemminger & Harold 1876: 3667.

Metriona effusa: Spaeth 1914b: 143.

Metriona Baeri: Spaeth 1915: 240.

Metriona circumdata ab. *pescadorensis* Chûjô 1934: 162.

Cassida cuticula Gressitt, 1938: 191. **Type locality:** Hainan, China.

Cassida (Taiwania) circumdata: Gressitt 1952: 489.

Taiwania (s. str.) *circumdata*: Chen & Zia 1961: 440.

Cassida nilgiriensis Borowiec & Takizawa, 1991: 642. **Type locality:** Cherangade, India.

Cassida (Crepidaspis) circumdata: Ghate *et al.* 2003: 526.

Cassida circumdata circumdata: Borowiec & Sekerka 2010: 373.

Material examined. Guangxi, Baise City, Leye County, Xinhua Town, Baini Village (乐业县新化镇百坭村), VIII.12.2024, 1♂1♀, leg. Guang-Lin Xie; Guangxi, Hechi City, Du'an County, Baoan Township (都安县保安乡), 18.VI.2024, 1♀, leg. Guang-Lin Xie.

Diagnosis. Body oval. Pronotum elliptical, pale yellow, with a central black disc shaped like an anchor. Scutellum triangular, black. Elytra with a U-shaped discal black spot; punctures coarse, arranged in regular longitudinal rows. Ventral surface and legs pale yellow; claws appendiculate. Frons bell-shaped. Antennae pale yellow.

Distribution. China: Fujian, Guangdong, Guangxi, Guizhou, Hainan, Hubei, Hunan, Jiangsu, Jiangxi, Sichuan, Taiwan, Yunnan, Zhejiang; Bangladesh; India; Indonesia; Japan; Laos; Malaysia; Nepal; Philippines; Sri Lanka; Thailand; Vietnam.

8) *Cassida obtusata* Boheman, 1854 柑桔台龟甲

Fig. 8

Cassida obtusata Boheman, 1854: 405.

Cassida Juno [sic] Boheman, 1862: 324. **Type locality:** Hong Kong, China.

Cassida pusillula Boheman, 1862: 327. **Type locality:** India.

Cassida interstitialis Spaeth, 1901: 12. **Type locality:** Sumatra, Indonesia.

Cassida residua Weise, 1901: 53. **Type locality:** Negombo, Sri Lanka.

Cassida (Odontionycha) picifrons Weise, 1908: 259. **Type locality:** Manila, Philippines.

Cassida (Cassida) juno: Spaeth 1914b: 114.

Cassida (Cassida) obtusata: Spaeth 1914b: 114.

Cassida (Cassida) residua: Spaeth 1914b: 114.

Cassida (Taiwania) obtusata: Gressitt 1952: 497.

Taiwania (s. str.) obtusata: Chen & Zia 1961: 440.

Material examined. Guangxi, Baise City, Leye County, Xinhua Town, Baini Village (乐业县新化镇百坭村), VIII.12.2024, 1♂1♀, leg. Guang-Lin Xie.

Diagnosis. Body elliptical, entirely pale yellow. Pronotum narrowly fusiform, disc smooth. Scutellum triangular. Elytra slightly broader than pronotum at base; disc slightly convex; punctures coarse, arranged in regular longitudinal rows. Metaventre black; abdominal median area black with pale lateral margins. Legs pale yellow; claws appendiculate. Frons elongate, twice as long as wide. Antennae pale yellow, apical four segments dark brown.

Distribution. China: Fujian, Guangdong, Guangxi, Hainan, Hong Kong, Jiangxi, Taiwan, Yunnan; Cambodia; India; Indonesia; Japan; Laos; Malaysia; Myanmar; Nepal; Philippines; Sri Lanka; Thailand; Vietnam.

9) *Cassida versicolor* (Boheman, 1855) 苹果台龟甲

Fig. 9

Coptocycla versicolor Boheman, 1855: 414. **Type locality:** China.

Coptocycla Thais [sic] Boheman, 1862: 463. **Type locality:** China.

Metriona thais: Spaeth 1914b: 144.

Metriona versicolor: Spaeth 1914: 144.

Metriona (Metriona) thais: Chûjô 1934: 160.

Thlaspida chinensis Gressitt, 1938: 385.

Cassida (Taiwania) versicolor: Gressitt 1952: 502.

Taiwania (s. str.) *versicolor*: Chen & Zia 1961: 440.

Material examined. Guangxi, Hechi City, Huanjiang Maonan Autonomous County, Chuanshan Town, Baidan Village, Baidan Guanhu Station (环江县川山镇白丹村白丹管护站), VIII.12.2024, 1♀, leg. Guang-Lin Xie.

Diagnosis. Body elliptical. Pronotum fusiform, lateral angles broadly rounded; discal dark brown in midposterior region, impunctate. Scutellum triangular, brownish-yellow. Elytral disc dark brown, interspersed with prominent pale yellow spots; punctures coarse, arranged in regular longitudinal rows; disc weakly tumid with a distinct X-shaped tubercle at apex, pale yellow. Epipleura with a large black spot in midposterior region. Ventral surface pale brownish-yellow. Legs pale yellow; claws appendiculate. Frons trapeziform. Antennae pale yellow; last segment blackish-brown.

Distribution. China: Fujian, Guangdong, Guangxi, Guizhou, Hainan, Heilongjiang, Hubei, Hunan, Jiangxi, Sichuan, Taiwan, Yunnan, Zhejiang; Japan; Laos; Myanmar; North Korea; Russia (Far East); Vietnam.

10) *Cassida vespertina* Boheman, 1862 山楂肋龟甲

Fig. 10

Cassida vespertina Boheman, 1862: 357. **Type locality:** China.

Deloyala vespertina: Weise 1900: 295.

Deloyale [sic] *vespertina*: Spaeth 1914a: 19.

Cassida (*Deloyala*) *vespertina*: Spaeth 1914b: 95.

Cassida (*Lasiocassis*) *vespertina*: Gressitt 1952: 486.

Cassida (*Alledoya*) *vespertina*: Gressitt & Kimoto 1963: 969.

Alledoya vespertina: Chen *et al.* 1986: 548.

Material examined. Guangxi, Baise City, Leye County, Xinhua Town, Baini Village (乐业县新化镇百坭村), VIII.12.2024, 1♀, leg. Guang-Lin Xie.

Diagnosis. Body oval. Pronotum narrowly elliptical, ochraceous brown; lateral angles broadly rounded. Scutellum lingulate, ochraceous brown. Elytral disc dark brown with coarse longitudinal carinae; strongly tumid, apex rounded. Explanate margin dark brown at base, mid-posterior region, and suture angle. Ventral surface blackish brown. Legs smoky brown; claws simple. Frons bell-shaped. Antennae smoky brown, apical four segments blackish.

Distribution. China: Beijing, Chongqing, Fujian, Gansu, Guangdong, Guangxi, Guizhou, Hebei, Heilongjiang, Hubei, Hunan, Inner Mongolia, Jiangsu, Jiangxi, Shaanxi, Sichuan, Taiwan, Zhejiang; Japan; Mongolia; North Korea; Russia (Far East).

Genus *Thlaspida* Weise, 1899 尾龟甲属

11) *Thlaspida biramosa* (Boheman, 1855) 双枝尾龟甲

Fig. 11

Coptoicycla bi-ramosa [sic] Boheman, 1855: 408. **Type locality:** Pulo Penang = Penang Island, Penang, Malaysia.

Thlaspida tristis Weise, 1899: 273. **Type locality:** Sumatra, Indonesia.

Thlaspida Formosae [sic] Spaeth, 1913: 46. **Type locality:** Taiwan, China.

Thlaspida biramosa: Spaeth 1914a: 17.

Thlaspida biramosa var. *tristis* Spaeth 1914a: 17.

Thlaspida japonica Spaeth, 1914a: 17. **Type locality:** Japan.

Thlaspida chinensis Spaeth, 1926: 64. **Type locality:** Sichuan, China.

Thlaspida formosae ab. *immaculatipennis* Chûjô, 1934: 157. **Type locality:** Sumatra, Indonesia.

Thlaspida biramosa chinensis: Gressitt 1952: 474.

Thlaspida biramosa japonica: Gressitt 1952: 475.

Thlaspida cribrosa: Medvedev 1957: 553.

Thlaspidia biramosa omeia Chen & Zia, 1964: 131. **Type locality:** “omeia” [= Emei Mountain], Sichuan, China.

Thlaspidia biramosa formosae: Takizawa 1978: 602.

Thlaspidia biramosa biramosa: Chen *et al.* 1986: 561, 634.

Material examined. Guangxi, Baise City, Leye County, Yachang Township (乐业县雅长乡), 17.IV.2024, 1♂1♀, leg. Guang-Lin Xie; Guangxi, Baise City, Leye County, Yachang Township, Yigou (乐业县雅长乡一沟), 8.VIII.2024, 1♂1♀, leg. Guang-Lin Xie; Guangxi, Baise City, Leye County, Yachang Township, Xinchang Village (乐业县雅长乡新场村), 10.VIII.2024, 1♂3♀♀, leg. Guang-Lin Xie; Guangxi, Hechi City, Nandan County, Baxuyaozu Township, Chaofang Village, Qiaoxiatun (南丹县八圩瑶族乡桥下屯), 2.VIII.2024, 1♀, leg. Guang-Lin Xie.

Diagnosis. Body elliptical. Pronotum narrowly elliptical, chestnut brown; disc smooth. Scutellum triangular, chestnut brown. Elytral disc strongly tumid, punctures coarse, arranged in regular longitudinal rows; apex with a rounded tubercle. Explanate margin of elytra with a large chestnut brown spot in mid-posterior region. Ventral surface mostly blackish brown, with pale pleura of prothorax, lateral margins and apical margin of abdomen pale. Legs chestnut brown; claws simple. Antennae chestnut brown, segments 7–11 blackish-brown.

Distribution. China: Anhui, Fujian, Guangdong, Guangxi, Guizhou, Hainan, Hubei, Hunan, Jiangsu, Jiangxi, Sichuan, Taiwan, Yunnan, Zhejiang; India; Japan; Laos; Malaysia; Myanmar; North Korea; Thailand; Vietnam.

Tribe Hispini Gyllenhal, 1813 铁甲族 Genus *Dactylispa* Weise, 1897 趾铁甲属

12) *Dactylispa feae* (Gestro, 1888) 黄黑趾铁甲

Fig. 12

Hispa feae Gestro, 1888: 183. **Type locality:** Bhamo, Myanmar.

Dactylispa filiola Weise, 1897: 135. **Type locality:** Kanara, India.

Dactylispa feae: Weise 1897: 149.

Hispa filiola: Donckier 1899: 605.

Dactylispa flavomaculata Uhmman, 1930: 133. **Type locality:** Lang Ha, Vietnam.

Di cladispa feae: Anand 1997: 9.

Di cladispa piliola [sic] Anand 1997: 9.

Material examined. Guangxi, Baise City, Leye County, Yachang Township, Yigou (乐业县雅长乡一沟), 8.VIII.2024, 1♂, leg. Guang-Lin Xie.

Diagnosis. Body elongate-oval; pale. Pronotum longer than wide, disc densely punctured with pale pubescence; midline black. Prothoracic spines 2:3 (apices black). Scutellum black, triangular, apex rounded with a circular depression. Elytral punctures arranged in regular longitudinal rows, 8 rows at midline; interstria II with 3 large spines, interspersed with small pale spines; interstria IV with 3 spines; interstria VI bearing 4 spines at humerus (first spine pale), followed by 2 spines; interstria VIII with 2 large spines; lateral and apical margins bearing ~13 small marginal spines, pale. Ventral surface mostly blackish-brown. Legs pale yellow. Antennae black on basal five segments.

Distribution. China: Fujian, Guangdong, Guangxi, Hainan, Hunan, Jiangxi, Sichuan, Taiwan, Yunnan; Cambodia; India; Indonesia; Laos; Malaysia; Myanmar; Sri Lanka; Thailand; Vietnam.

Genus *Platypria* Guérin-Ménéville, 1840 掌铁甲属

13) *Platypria aliena* Chen & Sun, 1962 并蒂掌铁甲

Fig. 13

Platypria aliena Chen & Sun, 1962: 130. **Type locality:** Xishuangbanna, China.

FIGURES 9–13. **9** *Cassida versicolor* (Boheman, 1855) **10** *C. vespertina* Boheman, 1862 **11** *Thlaspida biramosa* (Boheman, 1855) **12** *Dactylispa feae* (Gestro, 1888) **13** *Platypria aliena* Chen & Sun, 1962.

Material examined. Guangxi, Baise City, Leye County, Yachang Township (乐业县雅长乡), 8.VIII.2024, 3♀♀, leg. Guang-Lin Xie.

Diagnosis. Body yellow-brown. Pronotum nearly as long as wide; disc with 4 black spots, covered with pale recumbent pubescence; prothoracic lateral lobe with 6 spines each, bearing 4 window-like fenestrae. Scutellum triangular, apex rounded. Elytral disc punctures coarse, arranged in 10 regular longitudinal rows. Disc with spines and tubercles, II with a large spine in the middle; a very small one anteriorly and a median-sized one near apex; IV with 2 large spines and a small tubercle; VI with 2 small tubercles and 4 humeral spines; VIII with 2 small tubercles and a median-sized spine posteriorly; para-scutellar spines 2. Elytra with 6 spines in each anterior lobe and four fenestrae; posterior lobe with four spines and three fenestrae; apical margin with 6 small spines. Ventral surface and

legs pale yellow. Antennae pale yellow, segments 1, 2 and 9–11 dark brown.

Distribution. China: Guangxi (new province record), Yunnan.

Remarks. This species is known only from the type locality (Chen *et al.* 1962) and has not been collected or reported since its original description. The newly collected specimens supplement the species' distribution data and provide new insights into its habitat preferences.

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